

Certain summability methods in gradual normed spaces

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Abstract

Let $\lambda = (\lambda_n)$ denote a non-decreasing sequence of positive numbers such that (i) $\lambda_1 = 1$, (ii) $\lambda_{n+1} = \lambda_n + 1$, and (iii) $\lambda_n \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Using this sequence, in the present paper we aim to define $\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma: \mathcal{G})$ -summable, $\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})$ -summable and $\mathcal{J}(V_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})$ -summable sequences in gradual normed spaces and obtain some relevant connection.

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1 Introduction and Preliminaries

Fortin et al. [1] gave the concept of gradual numbers to deal with complex uncertainty and vagueness in complex data. They considered fuzzy intervals as crisp sets of entities instead of fuzzy sets. These numbers have wide applications in the examination of fuzzy intervals, soft computing, pattern recognition, control systems, and fuzzy optimization theory. "A gradual real number \tilde{n} is an assignment function $A_{\tilde{n}}: (0,1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Let $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ denote the set of all gradual real numbers. In addition, any $\tilde{n} \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ is said to be positive if $A_{\tilde{n}}(\eta) \geq 0$ for $\eta \in (0,1]$. Let $\mathcal{G}^*(\mathbb{R})$ denote the set of such numbers. For $\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2 \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$, $\tilde{n}_1 \circ \tilde{n}_2 \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ is defined by $A_{\tilde{n}_1 \circ \tilde{n}_2}(\eta) = A_{\tilde{n}_1}(\eta) \circ A_{\tilde{n}_2}(\eta)$ for $\eta \in (0,1]$; where $A_{\tilde{n}_1 \circ \tilde{n}_2}$ denotes the assignment function of $\tilde{n}_1 \circ \tilde{n}_2 \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$. Similarly, $\tilde{n}_1 + \tilde{n}_2$ and $c\tilde{n}_1$ for $\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2 \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ and $c \in \mathbb{R}$ are defined by $A_{\tilde{n}_1 + \tilde{n}_2}(\eta) = A_{\tilde{n}_1}(\eta) + A_{\tilde{n}_2}(\eta)$ for $\eta \in (0,1]$ and $A_{c\tilde{n}_1}(\eta) = cA_{\tilde{n}_1}(\eta)$ for $\eta \in (0,1]$. Moreover, if $A_{\tilde{l}}(\eta) = l$ for $\eta \in (0,1]$, then \tilde{l} is called the constant gradual real number." Using the above operations on $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ Sadeqi and Azari [10] defined the gradual normed linear space as follows:

Definition 2.1. "Let \mathcal{X} be a real vector space. The function $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}^*(\mathbb{R})$ is said to be a gradual norm on \mathcal{X} , if for every $\eta \in (0,1]$, following three properties are satisfied for any $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$

$$(\mathcal{G}_1) A_{\|x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) = A_{\tilde{0}}(\eta) \text{ iff } x = \theta, \text{ the zero vector of } \mathcal{X};$$

$$(\mathcal{G}_2) A_{\|\lambda x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) = |\lambda| A_{\|x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \text{ for any } \lambda \in \mathbb{R};$$

$$(\mathcal{G}_3)A_{\|x+y\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \leq A_{\|x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + A_{\|y\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta).$$

The pair $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is called a gradual normed linear space or briefly *GNLS*."

Let $\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{R}^n$, $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $0 < \eta \leq 1$. If $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ on \mathbb{R}^n is defined by

$$A_{\|x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) = e^{\eta} \sum_{j=1}^n |x_j|,$$

then Sadeqi and Azari [2] have shown that $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is a *GNLS*. "A sequence $w = (t_k)$ in *GNLS*: $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is said to be convergent to t_0 w.r.t the gradual norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$, if for every $\eta \in (0,1]$ and $\epsilon > 0$, there exist $m \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t $A_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \epsilon, \forall k \geq m$. In this case, we write $\mathcal{G} - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$." "A sequence $t = (t_k)$ in *GNLS*: $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is said to be Cauchy w.r.t gradual norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$, if for every $\eta \in (0,1]$ and $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t $A_{\|t_k - t_m\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \epsilon, \forall k, m \geq m_0$."

On the other side, Fast [3] presented a method of summation for divergent sequences using density of subsets of \mathbb{N} , called statistical convergence. The idea was further developed by several authors including Fridy [4, 7], Connor [5], Fridy and Orhan [6], Savaş and Nuray [8], and Mursaleen [9]. "A sequence $t = (t_k)$ of numbers is said to converge statistically to a number t_0 if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} |\{k \leq n: |t_k - t_0| \geq \epsilon\}|_c = 0$$

where $|\cdot|_c$ denotes the cardinality of the enclosed set. In this case, we will write $S - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$ or simply $t_k \rightarrow t_0(S)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$."

Let \mathbb{Z}^+ denote the set of positive integers, l_{∞} , the space of all bounded real sequences of numbers, and $\sigma: \mathbb{Z}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^+$ is a map. "A continuous linear functional φ on l_{∞} is called an σ -mean or invariant mean if it satisfies the following:

- (i) $\varphi(t) \geq 0$ where $t = (t_n)$ with $t_n \geq 0$ for all n ;
- (ii) $\varphi(t) = 1$ if $t = (t_n)$ with $t_n = 1$ for all n and
- (iii) $\varphi((t_{\sigma^m(n)})) = \varphi(t)$ if $t = (t_n)$ is in l_{∞} ."

The map φ is injective and $\sigma^m(n) \neq n, \forall m$ and n . If the map is defined by $\sigma: n \rightarrow n + 1$, then σ -mean is usually called a Banach limit.

Savaş and Nuray [8] used σ -mean to define an interesting generalization of statistical convergence with the help of lacunary sequences as follows: "Let $\vartheta = (\vartheta_r)$ be a lacunary sequence, i.e., a sequence of positive integers satisfying $\vartheta_0 = 0, h_r = \vartheta_r - \vartheta_{r-1} \rightarrow \infty$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$. Denote $I_r = (\vartheta_{r-1}, \vartheta_r]$ and the ratio $q_r = \vartheta_r / \vartheta_{r-1}$. A sequence $t = (t_k)$ of numbers is said to be lacunary statistically convergent to a number t_0 if for each $\epsilon > 0$,

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{h_r} |\{k \in I_r : |t_{\sigma^k(n)} - t_0| \geq \epsilon\}|_c = 0.$$

In this case, we write $S_\sigma(\vartheta) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$ or $t_k \rightarrow t_0(S_\sigma(\vartheta))$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

Kostryko et al [10] gave another generalization of statistical convergence using ideals. "For any nonempty set X , let $\mathcal{P}(X)$ denote the power set of X . A family of subsets $\mathcal{J} \subset \mathcal{P}(X)$ is said to be ideal in X if and only if (i) $\emptyset \in \mathcal{J}$; (ii) for each $T_1, T_2 \in \mathcal{J}$, $T_1 \cup T_2 \in \mathcal{J}$; (iii) for each $T_1 \in \mathcal{J}$ and $T_2 \subseteq T_1$ implies $T_2 \in \mathcal{J}$. Moreover, A family of subsets $\mathcal{F} \subset \mathcal{P}(X)$ is called a filter on X if and only if (i) $\emptyset \notin \mathcal{F}$; (ii) for each $T_1, T_2 \in \mathcal{F}$, $T_1 \cap T_2 \in \mathcal{F}$; (iii) for each $T_1 \in \mathcal{F}$ and $T_1 \subseteq T_2$ implies $T_2 \in \mathcal{F}$. An ideal \mathcal{J} is called nontrivial if $\mathcal{J} \neq \emptyset$ and $X \notin \mathcal{J}$. The filter $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J}) = \{X - A : A \in \mathcal{J}\}$ is called the filter associated with the ideal \mathcal{J} . A non-trivial ideal $\mathcal{J} \subset \mathcal{P}(X)$ is called an admissible ideal in X if and only if $\{\{x\} : x \in X\} \in \mathcal{J}$. For a non-trivial admissible ideal $\mathcal{J} \subset \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$, A real sequence $t = (t_k)$ is said to be \mathcal{J} -convergent to t_0 if for each $\epsilon > 0$, the set $A(\epsilon) = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : |t_k - t_0| \leq \epsilon\} \in \mathcal{J}$. In this case, we write $\mathcal{J} - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$."

Let $\lambda = (\lambda_n)$ denote a non-decreasing sequence of positive numbers such that (i) $\lambda_1 = 1$, (ii) $\lambda_{n+1} = \lambda_n + 1$, and (iii) $\lambda_n \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Using this sequence, in the present paper we aim to define $\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma; \mathcal{G})$ -summable, $\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma; \lambda; \mathcal{G})$ -summable and $\mathcal{J}(V_\sigma; \lambda; \mathcal{G})$ -summable sequences in gradual normed spaces and obtain some relevant connection.

2 Main Results

In what follows, by σ we will denote an invariant mean or σ mean, $\mathcal{J} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$ an admissible ideal, $\lambda = (\lambda_n)$ a nondecreasing sequence as described above, and $(\Omega, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ be any arbitrary GNLS.

Definition 2.1 A sequence $\omega = (\omega_k)$ in $(\Omega, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is said to be \mathcal{J} -sigma statistical summable or $\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma; \mathcal{G})$ -summable to ω_0 w.r.t $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ if for $\epsilon > 0$, $\gamma > 0$ and $0 < \zeta \leq 1$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{n} \left| \left\{ 0 \leq k \leq n : \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right| \geq \gamma \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$$

uniformly in $m = 1, 2, \dots$

We denote it by $\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma; \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \omega_k = \omega_0$ or simply $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0$ ($\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma; \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\text{Let } [\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma; \mathcal{G})] = \left\{ \omega = (\omega_k) \in \Omega : \mathcal{J}(S_\sigma; \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \omega_k \text{ exists} \right\}$$

uniformly in $m = 1, 2, \dots$

Definition 2.2 A sequence $\omega = (\omega_k)$ in $(\Omega, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is said to be \mathcal{J} -lambda sigma statistical summable or $\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma; \lambda; \mathcal{G})$ -summable to ω_0 w.r.t $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ if for $\epsilon > 0$, $\gamma > 0$ and $0 < \zeta \leq 1$

$$\left\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_G}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c \geq \gamma \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$$

uniformly in $m = 1, 2, \dots$

We denote it by $\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \omega_k = \omega_0$ or simply $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0$ ($\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\text{Let, } [\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})] = \left\{ \omega = (\omega_k) \in \Omega : \mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \omega_k \text{ exists} \right\}$$

uniformly in $m = 1, 2, \dots$

Definition 2.3 A sequence $\omega = (\omega_k)$ in $(\Omega, \|\cdot\|_G)$ is said to be \mathcal{J} -lambda strongly σ -summable or $\mathcal{J}(V_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})$ -summable to ω_0 w.r.t $\|\cdot\|_G$ if for $\epsilon > 0, \gamma > 0$ and $0 < \zeta \leq 1$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_G}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$$

uniformly $m = 1, 2, \dots$

We denote it by, $\mathcal{J}(V_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \omega_k = \omega_0$ or simply $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0$ ($\mathcal{J}(V_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

Let

$$[\mathcal{J}(V_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})] = \left\{ \omega = (\omega_k) \in \Omega : \mathcal{J}(V_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \omega_k \text{ exists, uniformly } m = 1, 2, \dots \right\}.$$

Theorem 2.5 $[\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \mathcal{G})], [\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})]$ and $[\mathcal{J}(V_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})]$ are linear spaces.

Proof. We prove the result for $[\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})]$ and the other two cases can be proved similarly. Let $\omega = (\omega_k), \tau = (\tau_k) \in [\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \mathcal{G})]$ and α, β be any two nonzero scalars (as otherwise, i.e., if $\alpha = \beta = 0$ or one of α and β is zero, the case follows easily). There exists ω_0 and $\tau_0 \in \Omega$ s.t for each $\epsilon > 0, \gamma > 0$ and $0 < \zeta \leq 1$

$$T_1 = \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_G}(\zeta) \geq \frac{\epsilon}{|\alpha|} \right\} \right|_c \geq \frac{\gamma}{2} \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$$

$$T_2 = \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|\tau_{\sigma^k(m)} - \tau_0\|_G}(\zeta) \geq \frac{\epsilon}{|\beta|} \right\} \right|_c \geq \frac{\gamma}{2} \right\} \in \mathcal{J};$$

uniformly in $m = 1, 2, \dots$

$$\text{Let, } T = \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|(\alpha \omega_{\sigma^k(m)} + \beta \tau_{\sigma^k(m)}) - (\alpha \omega_0 + \beta \tau_0)\|_G}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c \geq \gamma \right\},$$

then $T \subseteq T_1 \cup T_2$ and so in \mathcal{J} . This shows that $[\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})]$ is linear space.

The next Theorem permits the following relationships in the spaces $[\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \mathcal{G})], [\mathcal{J}(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G})]$ and $[\mathcal{J}(V_\sigma : \mathcal{G})]$.

Theorem 2.6 For any sequence $\omega = (\omega_k)$ in Ω , we have the following.

- (i) $[J(V_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})] \subset [J(S_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})]$ and the inclusion is proper.
- (ii) In addition, if $\omega = (\omega_k)$ is bounded in Ω w.r.t. the gradual norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0$ ($J(S_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})$), then $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0$ ($J(V_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})$), i.e., $[J(S_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})] \subseteq [J(V_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})]$.
- (iii) $[J(S_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})] \cap l_\infty(\mathcal{G}) = [J(V_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})] \cap l_\infty(\mathcal{G})$,
where $l_\infty(\mathcal{G})$ denotes the space of bounded sequences in Ω w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$.

Proof. (i) Assume $\omega = (\omega_k)$ in Ω be s.t $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0$ ($J(V_\sigma: \lambda: \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$. Then for $\epsilon > 0$ and $0 < \zeta \leq 1$

$$\left\{n \in \mathbb{N}: \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon\right\} \in \mathcal{J} \quad (1)$$

uniformly $m = 1, 2, \dots$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) &= \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon}} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \\ &\quad + \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) < \epsilon}} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \\ &\geq \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon}} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \\ &\geq \epsilon |\{k \in I_n: \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c. \end{aligned}$$

This gives for each $\gamma > 0$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n: \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c \geq \gamma \text{ implies}$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \gamma = \epsilon^* \text{ (say)}$$

and so

$$\left\{n \in \mathbb{N}: \frac{1}{\lambda_n} |\{k \in I_n: \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \geq \gamma\right\}$$

$$\subseteq \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon^* \right\}.$$

By (2), the later set is in \mathcal{J} , which implies the former set also in \mathcal{J} and therefore $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0 (J(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G}))$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

(ii) Let $\omega = (\omega_k)$ is bounded w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0 (J(S_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G}))$. Let $M > 0$ s.t for for all k, m and $0 < \zeta \leq 1$

$$\mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \leq M \tag{2}$$

and for $\epsilon > 0, \gamma > 0$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c \geq \gamma \right\} \in \mathcal{J}. \tag{3}$$

uniformly in $m = 1, 2, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) &= \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \frac{\epsilon}{2}}} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) < \frac{\epsilon}{2}}} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \\ &\leq \frac{M}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \frac{\epsilon}{2} \right\} \right|_c + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{by(3)}$$

and so

$$\begin{aligned} &\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \\ &\subseteq \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c \geq \frac{\epsilon}{2M} \right\} \in \mathcal{J} \\ &\tag{by(4) for } \gamma = \frac{\epsilon}{2M}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|\omega_{\sigma^k(m)} - \omega_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\zeta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$$

and therefore, we have $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_0 (J(V_\sigma : \lambda : \mathcal{G}))$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

(iii) This is a direct implication of (i) and (ii).

Conclusion

The gradual norm follows a flexible structure compared to the classical norm and is used to model complex problems that have gradual or smooth variations. Gradual norms are widely used to optimize gradual differences in signal processing, machine learning, approximation theory, function spaces, mathematical optimize, mathematical economics, game theory, and generalized data spaces. In the present work, we defined generalized sums in gradual normed spaces which can be used to examine various distance and convergence related problems where the usual convergence and the classical norm fails and we look forward towards a generalized norm such as the gradual norm.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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